

Generation Z – Chance oder Challenge?

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Quality of Applied Research and its Regional Impact

At a workshop on 25 September 2024 in Brussels, a subgroup of the CoARA working group “Towards Transformations” attempted to differentiate between different spheres of interest which may mask or override the quality assessment of applied research and discussed initial criteria for assessing the regional impact of applied research.

Dr. Thomas Brunotte, Dr. John Edwards, Dr. Martin Jaekel and Dominik Koc

A first difficulty for the evaluation of applied research that has a regional impact is the overlapping of spheres of interest (Fig. 1). It is not uncommon for applied research with a regional impact to be integrated into regional development policy. However, the specific objectives of a regional development policy must not be congruent with objectives inherent to science. What is of value for regional development does not necessarily have to be of scientific value – and vice versa. Such research is often also linked to institutional strategies, e. g. the specific goals of a university that wants to establish itself as an important reference partner in a particular region and foster regional development. It is not uncommon for funding structures to play a role, e. g. by stipulating certain thematic settings or prescribing forms of work such as project work. And research work that is often organised in project form is accompanied by its own structures and specifications. The regional impact of applied research therefore encounters a high density of external requirements and wishes that can mask or override academic creativity and originality. However, this does not rule out the possibility that applied research with a regional focus can exhibit a high degree of creativity and originality as well as research quality.

Figure 1:
Overlapping spheres of interest

The institutional framework

In a first keynote Robert Tijssen, Professor Emeritus, Leiden University, presented an analytic model of regional engagement and impact processes at the institutional level. Tijssen highlighted that it is important to incorporate a wide variety of sources of information including qualitative and quantitative aspects. Combining the results of two pilot studies (Regional Innovation Impact of Universities, UASiMAP) and a survey in which

30 Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) including 20 large universities and 10 smaller Universities of Applied Sciences (UAS) were asked to produce a self-assessment report, the following types of indicators were mentioned: Regional engagement and

outreach; Research, Entrepreneurship and Innovation; and Education and Human Resources. Tijssen also distinguished between impact potential from a prospective view giving a formative assessment (e. g. consortia, alliances, and platforms with external partner or dedicated facilities and infrastructures on the qualitative side and the number of workspaces, the amount of funding or the share of research publications on the quantitative side) and impacts from a retrospective view providing a summative assessment (e. g. successful outreach activities and research-related contributions to local policy initiatives on the qualitative side and the number of graduates with jobs at regional employers and revenues by regional firms related to joint research-related innovations on the quantitative side).

Furthermore, Tijssen provided a definition of research-related regional impact of a higher education institution: “Research-related regional impact of a higher education institution is demonstrable and/or perceptible benefits to individuals, groups, organisations, and society (including human and non-human entities), which are located in a HEI’s local or regional geographic environment, in the present and future that are causally linked (necessarily or sufficiently) to research.”

Regional Policies

A second keynote within the workshop was held by Nicola Dotti from the European Commission, DG Research & Innovation, who summarised the so-called Science, Research and Innovation Performance Report of the European Union (SRIP report 2024). His focus was on the regional development policy level from a European perspective. Challenges that the European Union faces are an underutilised research and innovation ecosystem, the existence of a research and innovation divide, and a technological gap. Consequently, the Commission’s aim is to make trade-offs between excellence vs. concentration, directionality vs. diversification, and efficiency of allocating gains vs. expected long-term gains. The issue in Europe is how to find a balance between optimal levels of concentration

while still not exacerbating the already existing research and innovation divide, meaning that research and innovation can be concentrated in a region but needs to be distributed. While this approach is very understandable from a policy making perspective it is evident that such necessary balances between regions of the European Union must not match with research immanent developments and cannot be the sole criteria for assessing the quality of applied research. On the other hand, it cannot be denied that such aspects often play an important role in the design of funding programmes and in the selection of research projects to be funded, particularly in the case of cohesion funds which have a specific relevance for applied research. This can easily lead to a confusion between regional development policy and quality criteria for the evaluation of applied science. And, of course, this does not only apply to the level of the European Union; similar problems also exist in the member states and in the regions.

Epistemic Interest, Interest in Cooperation, and Measuring the Quality of Science

The two keynote speeches covered a wide range of aspects, enabling completely different perspectives on the assessment of the quality of applied research. While questions of networking and the anchoring of a University of Applied Sciences in the respective region play an important role in the institutional perspective, questions of innovative strength and political development goals are decisive for the quality assessment of applied research against the background of regional development policy. This naturally raises the question of how researchers themselves would view the quality of their work. Roughly speaking, a scientist is first and foremost looking for recognition in his or her respective (international) specialist research community. In contrast, questions of institutional integration or the alignment with regional development goals are less important. The focus here is on the epistemic interest, i. e. the further development of the state of knowledge in the respective discipline. Here, publications and bibliometric indicators have become established for measuring quality, which make transparent how often a research achievement

has been received in the context of the respective subject or beyond. In the case of applied research, however, other goals and motives can be added to this epistemic interest alone. This applies in particular to the establishment, utilisation, and further development of collaborations with partners outside the academia. Such co-operations do not necessarily have to relate to institutional goals or regional development policy. They can be of high quality and substance even without such references. Co-operation with partners outside the university often takes place in jointly developed projects, in which the project partners may have different expectations of the results and success of the respective project. Accordingly, different factors, expectations, and interests also play a role in the evaluation of the project and the quality of its results. However, such projects in particular can have a considerable influence on the regional impact of applied science, as most of what happens in the field of applied science between universities and their regional partners takes place in such projects. Aspects of what constitutes a good collaboration, e. g. the sustainability of the collaboration, the development of a joint product or result, or noticeable changes in the respective partner also play a role in the evaluation of the underlying, jointly conducted applied research. These need not be identical with aspects of the quality assessment of the work on the research question on which the collaboration is based. It is therefore necessary to broaden the view in such a way that, on the one hand, the evaluation standards inherent to the scientific interest are not overlaid and, on the other hand, the other quality evaluation factors that make up the cooperative character of applied science are not lost from view. This was the subject of discussion at the workshop.

Developing a Matrix of Assessment Criteria for Applied Research with Regional Impact

The workshop ended with a first sketch of a matrix for assessing applied research in its regional context. Parts of this matrix are drafted here. This overview is not complete and may well be improved, completed, or changed. Readers are invited to contact the corresponding author with their suggestions.

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Conclusion

In order to balance the different levels and spheres of interest involved in initiating, designing, conducting, funding, or managing applied research with regional impact it is important to be open to the creativity and originality that is inherent to research. When research is dominated from outside, i. e. policy preferences, institutional requirements, thematic focuses of funding initiatives, it might well be that in the end research

only generates more of the same and not what is new. Even in settings like these it must be possible to come up with something completely new. This may be discovering a new problem nobody has thought of before, a novel idea for an alternative solution, or an innovative method. Most likely, original findings like these will not occur in settings that are driven by a certain policy, predefined thematic scopes, or institutional requirements. It is important to give researchers a say beyond the framework of the aforementioned settings and to

Employment, Workforce & Education

Quantitative	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Potential number of new jobs created in the region through the research – Number of dual appointments professors/researchers in industry/professional practice – Number of theses addressing regional problems – Number of research projects addressing regional problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Business leaders' perspectives on new opportunities created by the research – Satisfaction of regional firms with research collaboration and results – New educational curricula/products developed from research (research lines, minors, masters, summer schools) – Can research project upgrade regional industry? – Use of research outputs in local education institutions – Can research project improve learning outcomes of students? – Tailor-made courses for regions (smart specialisation strategy present) as a result of research

Business and Industry

Quantitative	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of local companies using research results – Number of new start-ups or spin-offs in the region – Revenue of start-ups or spin-offs in the region – External financing of start-ups, spin-offs, spin-outs in the region – Survival rate of start-ups, spin-offs, spin-outs in the region – Growth rate of start-ups, spin-offs, spin-outs in the region – Revenue growth in regional firms as a result of applied research project – Number of workshops or training sessions provided to local businesses – Patents licensed to regional companies for commercial use – New products introduced by local firms using applied research – New services introduced by local firms using applied research – Funding or grants acquired for regional businesses (from outside the region) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Local firms reporting increased productivity after collaboration – Extent of follow-up action/commercialisation of theses in the region – Utilisation of research infrastructure and sharing – Mobility of researchers between public and private sectors

Consortia

Quantitative	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of other regions involved in research (other than home region) – Number of co-publications with private/public parties in region – Number of funded projects with local industry/non-academic organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Satisfaction of local partners in project consortia – Research cited in consultancy assignments with local companies or public institutions – Extent of collaboration with other local research institutions

Social Development

Quantitative	Qualitative
Community Engagement and Inclusion	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of community meetings or public forums about research projects – Research initiatives developed in response to (local) community needs – Proportion of research projects conducted in collaboration with local NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Community members' reported awareness of the institution's research projects – Increase in local community knowledge about research topics over time – Research specifically aimed at underrepresented community groups in the region
Education and Public Awareness	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of collaborative educational programs created with local schools – Creation of public information campaigns on research outcomes – Citizen Science events and local residents attending 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Attendance and feedback ratings for public workshops or lectures – Local media coverage frequency on applied research activities – Percentage of locals participating in lifelong learning programs – Reported trust in science of local residents as a result of researchers engagement

Environmental Impact

Quantitative	Qualitative
Sustainability and Resource Management	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of local businesses implementing sustainable practices from research – Frequency of regional sustainability workshops organized by researchers – Amount of sustainable technology adopted by regional industries based on research results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Community reports on reduced environmental pollution due to research
Climate Adaptation and Resilience	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Projects addressing climate resilience for local communities and businesses – Research initiatives designed to mitigate specific regional climate risks – Adoption rate of climate-resilient infrastructure in the region as a result of research

Cultural Impact and Health

Quantitative	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of research initiatives focused on local culture & heritage preservation – Research-driven initiatives for reducing regional social inequalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Changes in regional health indicators based on research

Policy and Governance

Quantitative	Qualitative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of local policy proposals informed by research outcomes – Growth in publications or reports informing local or regional governance – Research briefs or white papers used in local policy decisions – Public mentions of research in local government sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Alignment with regional/national/international agendas – Shared roadmaps/research agendas with other researchers or research institutions – Feedback from policymakers on the practical value of research for regional decision-making

Innovation and Knowledge Transfer

Quantitative	Qualitative
Knowledge Dissemination	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Number of research papers published in regional journals – Growth in regional academic citations of institution’s research – Presence of research results in local research newsletters or updates – Presence of research results in interdisciplinary workshops conducted for knowledge exchange 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Annual surveys showing increased public understanding of research areas
Technology Transfer	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Patents registered in the region as a result of applied research – Rate of regional uptake of new technologies or innovations from applied research – Research used in regional hackathons or innovation challenges – Local grants awarded for the commercialization of research technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Technology licensing agreements with local firms based on research results

provide room for creating something new. This can be achieved with small grant funding programmes offering seed money for exploring new ideas without the need to produce useful results. Failure is a possibility when new ideas and methods are explored. Success is

not guaranteed. Particularly within the field of research funding for applied research it is important to offer small grant funding schemes in addition to classic research project and project consortia that comply with external policies and funding preferences. ■

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